

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

FAST DISSOLVING SYSTEMS: FDT VS FDF

R. Santosh Kumar, Sahithi Mudili

GITAM Institute of Pharmacy, GITAM University, Rushikonda, Visakhapatnam-45.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 31/01/2018

Available online
28/02/2018

Keywords

Fast Dissolving Tablets,
Fast Dissolving Films,
Patented Technology.

ABSTRACT

Fast dissolving drug delivery systems are ideal for all types of people, including for people who have swallowing difficulties, pediatric, geriatric, and bedridden patients. It is also for active patients who are busy, travelling and may not have access to water. Fast dissolving drug delivery systems includes both fast dissolving tablets and fast dissolving films. This type of drug delivery system disintegrates quickly once introduced into the mouth in the absence of additional water for easy administration of active pharmaceutical ingredients. The active ingredients can be absorbed directly through oral mucosa into the systemic circulation bypassing the first pass metabolism. Hence, quicker onset of action, reduction in dosage and frequency, avoidance of gut wall and hepatic metabolism, and increase in bioavailability are eminent. This review article presents the common and differentiating features between the fast dissolving tablets (FDT) and fast dissolving films (FDF) and the list of common drugs which are manufacturing as both fast dissolving tablets and fast dissolving films.

Corresponding author

Dr. R. Santosh Kumar

GITAM Institute of Pharmacy,
GITAM University, Rushikonda,
Visakhapatnam-45, A.P, India.
radasantosh@rediffmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **Dr. R. Santosh Kumar et al.** Fast Dissolving Systems: FDT VS FDF. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(02).

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INTRODUCTION

Fast-dissolving drug-delivery systems were initially developed in the late 1970s as an alternative to tablets, capsules, and syrups for paediatric and geriatric patients who experiences difficulties in swallowing traditional oral solid-dosage forms. Fast dissolving drug delivery system (FDDS) is gaining popularity in pharmaceutical companies as they are new drug delivery technique in order to provide the patient with medicine without obstacles in swallowing. The speed of solubility of drug affects the rate of absorption of the drug. The faster the drug dissolve into solution, quicker the absorption and onset of clinical effect. They should readily dissolve or disintegrate in the saliva generally within <60 seconds. Fast dissolving drug delivery system includes both fast dissolving tablets and fast dissolving films. Fast dissolving tablets defined as a tablet that dissolves or disintegrates in the oral cavity without need of water or chewing^[1]. Fast dissolving tablets are also suitable when local action in the mouth is desirable such as local anaesthetic for oral ulcers, toothaches, cold sores, or teething and to those who cannot swallow intact sustained action tablets Fast dissolving films^[2] are most advance form of solid dosage form due to its flexibility. It improve efficacy of API dissolving in the short duration oral cavity after the contact with less amount of saliva as compared to dissolving tablet. This fast dissolving action is primarily due to the large surface area of the film, which wets quickly when exposed to themoistoral environment

Common Features between FDT & FDF: [3-5]

- Ease of administration to patients who refuse to swallow a tablet, such as pediatric and geriatric patients and, psychiatric patients.
- Convenience of administration and accurate dosing as compared to liquids.
- Rapid dissolution of drug and absorption which may produce rapid, onset of action
- Ability to provide advantages of liquid medication in form of solid preparation.
- Pre-gastric absorption can result in improved bioavailability and as a result of reduced dosage, improved clinical performance through a reduction of unwanted effects.^[6-8]
- Compatible with taste masking.^[9]
- Rapid drug therapy intervention^[9]
- Pleasant mouth feel^[9]
- Obstruction free: No risk of suffocation in airways due to physical obstruction when swallowed, thus providing improved safety and compliance^[9]
- Quick Disintegration: Fast action in comparison to conventional drugs.^[9]
- Noninvasive^[9]
- These are hygroscopic in nature so must be keep in dry place.
- FDT and FDF requires special packaging for properly stabilization & safety of stable product
- Cost effective.
- No risk of choking.

Table 1: Differentiation between FDT &FDF.

Fast Dissolving Tablets	Fast Dissolving Films
❖ Some time it possesses mouth feeling.	❖ Good mouth feel
❖ Good Drug Loading Capacity: Large amount of drug can be loaded.	❖ High dose cannot be incorporated into the oral film
❖ Simple packaging: No specific packaging required. It can be packaged in push through blisters	❖ They require special packaging for the products stability and safety
❖ Any drugs can be administered	❖ Drugs which are unstable at buccal pH cannot be administered.
❖ Small to moderate molecular weight drugs can be formulated into FDT	❖ Low molecular weight drugs can be incorporated into FDF
❖ Ability to diffuse and partition into the epithelium of the upper GIT	❖ Drugs which irritate the mucosa cannot be administered by this route.
❖ Available in traditional tablet shape	❖ Available in different size and shape
❖ Less surface area gives less dissolution than fast dissolving films.	❖ Large surface area gives greater dissolution
❖ Fast dissolving tablets are brittle and less durable than fast dissolving films	❖ Fast dissolving films are flexible and durable.
❖ Fast dissolving tablets are of same size of convenient tablet	❖ Fast dissolving films are of thickness 0.015 inches to 0.5 inches.
❖ Patient compliance is less than fast dissolving films	❖ Patient compliance is more.

Table-2: Composition of Fast Dissolving Tablets and Fast Dissolving Films.

Fast dissolving tablets	Fast dissolving films ^[2]
❖ API	❖ API (1-30%)
❖ Super disintegrants	❖ Polymers (40-50%)
❖ Bulking materials (10-90%)	❖ Plasticizer (0-20%)
❖ Emulsifying agent (0.05% to 15%)	❖ Surfactant (solubility enhancer) (Sufficient quantity)
❖ Lubricants	❖ Saliva stimulating agent (2-6%)
❖ Flavors	❖ Sweetening agent (3-6%)
❖ Sweeteners	❖ Flavoring agent (0-10%)
❖ Coloring agent	❖ Coloring agent (Sufficient qty)
❖ -	❖ Stabilizing agent or Thickening agent (0-5%)

Table-3: List of Drugs Used in Fast Dissolving Tablets and Fast Dissolving Films.

Drugs used in Fast dissolving tablets	Drugs used in Fast dissolving films
❖ Antibacterial agents: Ciprofloxacin, Tetracycline, Erythromycin, Rifampicin, Pencilin, Doxycyclin.	❖ 5HT ₃ Antagonists: Alosetron, Ondansetron, Granisetron, Palanosetron, Ramosetron, Triptosectron.
❖ Anti helminthics: Albendazole, Mebendazole, Thiobendazole, Livemectin, Praziquantel	❖ Anti-migraines: Almotriptan, Dihydroergotamine Mesylate, Eletriptan, Fravotriptan, Naratriptan, Rizatriptan, Sumatriptan and Zolmitriptan.
❖ Anti Depressants: Trimipramine Maleate, Nortriptyline HCl, Trazodone HCl, Amoxapine	❖ Anti-epileptics: Carbamazepine, Clonazepam, Diazepam, Divalproex Sodium, Fosphenytoin, Gabapentin, Lamotrigine, Levetiracetam, Oxcarbazepine, Phenytoin, Pregabalin
❖ Anti diabetics: Glibenclamide, Glipizide, Talbutamide, Chlorpropamide	❖ Statins: Atorvastatin, Cerivastatin, Fluvastatin, Lovastatin, Pitavastatin, Rosuvastatin
❖ Analgesics: Diclofenac Sodium, Ibuprofen, Ketoprofen, Mefenamic Acid, Naproxen, Oxyphenbutazone	❖ Dopamine D ₁ and D ₂ antagonists: Amisulpride, Bromperidol, Cabergoline, Domperidone, fenoldopam.
❖ Anti hypertensives: Amlodipine, Carvedilol, Diltiazem, Felodipine, Minoxidil, Nifedipine, Prazosin.	❖ Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors: Fluoxetine, Sertraline, Paroxetine, Fluvoxamine, Citalopram, Alaproclate.
❖ Antiarrhythmics: Disopyramide, Quinidine Sulphate, Amiodarone	

Table-4: List of Excipients Used in Preparation of Fast Dissolving Tablets and Fast Dissolving Films.

Fast dissolving tablets	Fast dissolving films
<p>Superdisintegrants:^[10,11]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ An important excipients of the tablet formulation ❖ Induce breakup of tablet when it comes in contact with aqueous fluid ❖ Increase surface area of the tablet fragments <p>Types of Superdisintegrants</p> <p>I. Natural</p> <p>II. Synthetic</p> <p>Natural superdisintegrants</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Lepidus Sativum, ❖ Locust Bean Gum, ❖ Isapgghula Husk (Plantago ovata) ❖ Hibiscus Rosa ❖ Sinesis Linn ❖ Mucilage ❖ Chitosan ❖ Orange Peel Pectin <p>Synthetic superdisintegrants</p> <p>Croscarmellose Sodium (Vivasol, Ac-Di-Sol)</p> <p>Crospovidone (Polypylasdone)</p> <p>Carmellose (NS-300),</p> <p>Carmellose Calcium (ECG-505)</p> <p>Sodium Starch Glycolate (SSG)</p> <p>Ion Exchange Resins (Indion 414)</p> <p>Mechanism of action of Super disintegrants :</p> <p>Capillary action^[16-18]</p> <p>Swelling^[18]</p> <p>Heat of wetting</p> <p>Disintegrating particle/particle repulsive forces^[16-17]</p> <p>Deformation^[18]</p> <p>Release of gases</p> <p>Enzymatic action</p> <p>Bulking materials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ They contribute the functions of a diluents, filler and cost reducer. ❖ Improve the texture of the tablets that consequently enhances the disintegration in the mouth. <p>Example:</p> <p>Mannitol,</p> <p>Polydextrose,</p> <p>Lactose derivatives such as Direct Compressible Lactose (DCL) Starch hydrolysate</p> <p>Microcrystalline cellulose</p> <p>Lactosemonohydrate</p> <p>Spray-dried lactose</p> <p>Anhydrous beta lactose</p> <p>Anhydrous alpha lactose</p> <p>Dicalcium phosphate dihydrate.</p> <p>Emulsifying agents:^[21]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Help in quick disintegration and drug release without the need for chewing, swallowing or drinking water. ❖ Emulsifying agents stabilize the immiscible blends and increase bioavailability. <p>Examples:</p>	<p>Film forming polymers:^[12]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Polymers are the most important ingredient of the oral fast dissolving film. ❖ Mainly hydrophilic polymers are used in the oral strip as they rapidly disintegrate in the oral cavity as they come in contact with saliva <p>Types of polymers:^[13-15]</p> <p>I. Natural polymers</p> <p>II. Synthetic polymers</p> <p>Natural polymers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Pullulan ❖ Starch gelatin ❖ Pectin ❖ Sodium alginate ❖ Maltodextrin ❖ Polymerized rosin ❖ Lycoat NG 73 ❖ Xanthan <p>Synthetic polymers:</p> <p>Hydroxypropylmethyl cellulose</p> <p>Polyvinyl pyrrolidone</p> <p>Polyvinyl alcohol</p> <p>Carboxy methyl cellulose</p> <p>Poly ethylene oxide</p> <p>Kollicoats</p> <p>Hydroxypropyl cellulose</p> <p>Hydroxyl ethyl cellulose</p> <p>Plasticizers:^[19-20]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Improve the flexibility and reduce the brittleness of the fast dissolving film ❖ Addition of Plasticizers, tensile strength and elongation can be improved. <p>Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Glycerol ❖ Di-butylphthalate ❖ Polyethylene glycols ❖ Dimethyl,Dicetyl,Dibutyle Pthalate <p>Saliva Stimulating Agent:^[22-23]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Increase the rate of production of saliva that would be aid in the faster disintegration of the fast dissolving film. <p>Examples:</p> <p>Citric acid</p>

Alkyl sulfates	Malic acid
Propylene glycol esters	Lactic acid
Lecithin	Ascorbic acid
Sucrose esters	Tartaric acid
Lubricants: ^[21]	Surfactant: ^[24]
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ They make the tablets more palatable after they disintegrate in the mouth. ❖ Lubricants reduce grittiness and help in the drug transit process from the oral to the stomach. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Used as solublising or wetting or dispersing agent so that the film is getting dissolved within seconds and release active agent immediately.
Flavors and Sweeteners: ^[21]	Examples:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Make the products more palatable and pleasing for patients. 	Sodium lauryl sulfate
Example for Sweeteners:	Benzalkonium chloride
Sugar	Bezthonium chloride
Dextrose	Tweens
Fructose	Spans
Aspartame	Sweetening Agent: ^[25-26]
Sodium saccharin,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Improve the palatability of the fast dissolving film.
Sugar alcohols	Examples:
Sucralose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Sorbitol ❖ Sucrose ❖ Cyclamate ❖ Aspartame ❖ Orange oil ❖ Melochite green
	Flavoring Agent: ^[27-28]
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Mask the taste of the film
	Examples:
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Peppermint oil ❖ Cinnamon oil ❖ Menthol ❖ Lemon oil ❖ Chloroform water
	Coloring Agent: ^[29]
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Titanium Dioxide ❖ Sunset yellow

Technologies Used for Preparation of Fast Dissolving Tablets and Fast Dissolving Films

Fast dissolving tablets:

Disintegrant addition:

Involves the addition of super disintegrants in optimum concentration to the formulation to achieve rapid disintegration/dissolution.

Examples:

- ❖ MCC and Sodium Starch Glycolate used in formulation of Efavirenz
- ❖ Crystalline cellulose (Avicel PH-102) and low substituted HPEC used in Oxybutinin and Piperzepine formulation

Freeze drying or lyophilization:^[30]

The drug is dissolved and dispersed in an aqueous solution carrier. The mixer is poured into the wells of the preformed blister packs. The trays holding the blister pack will pass through the liquid nitrogen freezing tunnel to freeze the drug solution. Then the frozen blister packs placed into the refrigerated cabinets to continue the freeze drying. The preparations are highly porous, have high specific surface area, dissolve rapidly and ultimately show improved absorption and bioavailability.

Moulding:^[31]

A water soluble ingredient with a hydro-alcoholic solvent are used and is molded into tablets under pressure lower than that used in conventional tablet compression. Molded tablets are very less compact than compressed tablet porous structure than enhances disintegration/dissolution and finally absorption increased.

Sublimation:^[32]

Inert solid ingredients that volatilize rapidly like Camphor Ammonium Carbonate, Ammonium bicarbonate, Hexamethyletetra Amine were added to the other tablet ingredients and the mixer is compressed into tablets. The volatile material was then removed via sublimation, which generates porous structure.

Spray drying: [33-34]

By hydrolyzed and non hydrolyzed gelatins as supporting agents, Mannitol as bulking agent, Sodium Starch Glycolate or Croscarmellose Sodium as disintegrating agent and an acidic material (Citric Acid) or alkali material (Sodium Bicarbonate) to enhance disintegration /dissolution. The tablets prepared in this method disintegrate within 20 sec when immersed in an aqueous medium.

Mass extrusion: [35]

Involves softening the active blend using the solvent mixture of water soluble Polyethylene Glycol, Methanol and expulsion of softened mass through the extruder or syringe to get a cylindrical shape of the product into even segments using heated blade to from tablets. The dried product can be used to coat granules of bitter tasting drugs and there by masking their bitter taste.

Direct Compression: [36-37]

Conventional equipment, commonly available excipients and a limited number of processing steps are involved in direct compression. It is most cost effective tablet manufacturing technique.

Cotton Candy Process: [38-39]

Involves the formation of matrix of polysaccharides by simultaneous action of flash melting and spinning. This candy floss matrix is then milled and blended with active ingredients and excipients after recrystallization and subsequently compressed to fast dissolving tablets. It can accommodate high doses of drug and offers improved mechanical strength.

Compaction:**Melt granulation:**

Prepared by incorporating a hydrophilic waxy binder (Super Polystate) PEG-6-Stearate. Super polystate not only act as binder and increased physical resistance of tablet but also helps the disintegration of tablet. It melts in mouth and solubilizes rapidly leaving no residue. [40]

Phase transition process:

Prepared by compressing powder containing two sugar alcohols with high and low melting points and subsequent heating at a temperature between their melting points. The tablet hardness was increased after heating process due to increase of inter particle bond induced by phase transition of lower melting points sugar alcohol. The compatibility increased and so sufficient hardness gained by the formulation.

Nanonization: [41]

Involves size reduction of drug to nano size by milling the drug using a proprietary wet milling technique. The nano crystals of the drug are stabilized against agglomeration by surface adsorption on selected stabilizers, which are then incorporated into FDTs. It is used for poorly water soluble drugs. It leads to higher bioavailability and reduction in dose, cost effective manufacturing process, conventional packing due to exceptional durability and wide range of doses (up to 200 mg of drug per unit).

Fast dissolving films:**Solvent casting method** [42]

In solvent casting method water soluble polymers are dissolved in water and the drug along with other Excipients is dissolved in suitable solvent then both the solutions are mixed and stirred and finally casted in to the Petri plate and dried.

Semisolid casting [43-44]:

In semisolid casting method firstly a solution of water soluble film forming polymer is prepared. The resulting solution is added to a solution of acid insoluble polymer (e.g. Cellulose Acetate Phthalate, Cellulose Acetate Butyrate), which was prepared in ammonium or sodium hydroxide. Then appropriate amount of plasticizer is added so that a gel mass is obtained. Finally the gel mass is casted in to the films or ribbons using heat controlled drums. The thickness of the film is about 0.015-0.05 inches. The ratio of the acid insoluble polymer to film forming polymer should be 1:4

Hot melt extrusion [45-46]:

In hot melt extrusion method firstly the drug is mixed with carriers in solid form. Then the extruder having heaters melts the mixture. Finally the melt is shaped in to films by the dies. There are certain benefits of hot melt extrusion are fewer operation units, Better content uniformity, an anhydrous process

Solid dispersion extrusion [47-48]

In this method immiscible components are extrude with drug and then solid dispersions are prepared. Finally the solid dispersions are shaped in to films by means of dies.

Rolling Method ^[49-50]

In rolling method a solution or suspension containing drug is rolled on a carrier. The solvent is mainly water and mixture of water and alcohol. The film is dried on the rollers and cutted in to desired shapes and sizes.

PATENTED TECHNOLOGIES**Fast dissolving tablets:****Zydis (Cardinal Health Inc.)** ^[51]

Zydis tablet is produced by lyophilizing the drug in a matrix usually consisting of gelatin. The product is very lightweight and fragile and must be dispensed in a special blister pack. Zydis formulation is also self-preserving because the final water concentration in the freeze-dried product is too low to allow for microbial growth. A water insoluble drug can be incorporated only up to 400 mg per tablet or less, On the other hand water soluble drug can be incorporated only up to 60 mg. The preferred drugs are water insoluble, low dose, chemically stable, small particle size and tasteless.

Lyoc (Cephalon Corporation) ^[52]

Lyoc utilizes a freeze drying process but differ from Zydis in that the product is frozen on the freeze dryer shelves. The liquid solution or suspension preparation evolves fillers, thickening agents, surfactant, non-volatile flavoring agents and sweeteners along with drug. This homogeneous liquid is placed in blister cavities and subjected to freeze drying. To prevent in homogeneity by sedimentation during this process, these formulations require a large proportion of un dissolved inert filler (Mannitol), to increase the viscosity of the in process suspension. The high proportion of filler reduces the potential porosity of the dried dosage form and results in denser tablets with disintegration rates are comparable to loosely compressed fast melt formulations.

Wowtab (Yamanouchi Pharma Technologies, Inc.) ^[53-54]

‘Wow’ means ‘without water’. The active ingredients may constitute up to 50% w/w of the tablet. The combination of high and low mouldability saccharides is used to produce tablets of adequate hardness & a rapidly melting strong tablet. Active ingredients are mixed with low mouldability saccharides (e.g. Mannitol, Lactose, Glucose, Sucrose, and Erythritol) and then granulated with high mouldability saccharides(e.g. Maltose, Maltitol, and Sorbitol). and then compressed into tablet. Wowtab product dissolves quickly in 15s or less. Wowtab product can be packed in both into conventional bottle and blister packs.

Flashtab (Prographarm) ^[55]

Flashtab involves coating a drug with a Eudragit polymer to provide rapid release of the drug in the stomach, and formulating this microencapsulated drug with an effervescent couple to produce a flash dispersal tablet. This technology includes granulation of excipients by wet or dry granulation method followed by compression into tablets. Disintegrating agents include Poly Vinylpyrrolidone or Carboxy methyl cellulose and Swelling agents include Carboxy Methylcellulose, Starch, Modified Starch, Microcrystalline Cellulose, Carboxy Methylated Starch etc. These tablets have satisfactory physical resistance. Tablets containing hygroscopic materials can also be blister packed using high quality polyvinyl chloride or aluminum foils for providing the higher degree of moisture protection than normal polyvinylchloride or polypropylene foils

Durasolv (Cima Labs, Inc.) ^[56]

DuraSolv has much higher mechanical strength than Orasolv due to the use of higher compaction pressures during tableting. DuraSolv is so durable that it can be packaged in either traditional blister packaging or vials. This technology is not compatible with larger doses of active ingredients, because the formulation is subjected to such high pressures on compaction. The tablets made by this technology consist of a drug, fillers and a lubricant and prepared by using conventional tableting equipment and have good rigidity.

Orasolv (Cima Labs, Inc.) ^[57]

It based on direct compression of an effervescent agent and taste masked drug. The use of effervescence causes a tablet to disintegrate rapidly in less than 1 min on contact with water or saliva leaving coated drug powder. This technology can accommodate a wide range of active ingredient from 1 mg to 500 mg. The effervescence occurs due to chemical reaction between organic acid such as Citric Acid, Fumaric Acid or Maleic Acid and a base such as Sodium Bicarbonate, Potassium Bicarbonate, and Magnesium Bicarbonate, which result in generation of CO₂. Micro particles, effervescent agents and other ingredient such as flavors, sweeteners, colorants and lubricants are blended and compressed at a low degree of compaction

Frosta (Akina) ^[58]

It utilizes the concept of formulating plastic granules and compressing them at low pressure to produce strong tablets with high porosity. Plastic granules composed of porous and plastic material, water penetration enhancer, and binder. The process involves mixing the porous plastic material with water penetration enhancer followed by granulating with binder. The tablets obtained have excellent hardness and rapid disintegration time ranging from 15 to 30 sec depending on size of tablet.

AdvaTab (Eurand) ^[59]

In this technology, microencapsulation process is used for coating the drug particles with gastro soluble polymer so as to mask the taste along with restriction of drug dissolution in mouth cavity. AdvaTab tablets disintegrate rapidly in the mouth, typically in less than 30 seconds.

Flashdose (Fuisz Technologies, Ltd.) ^[60-61]

This uses the combination of Shear form and Ceform technologies in order to mask the bitter taste of the drug. Flashdose technology utilizes a unique spinning mechanism to produce a floss-like crystalline structure, much like cotton candy. This crystalline sugar can then incorporate the active drug and be compressed into a tablet. It disperses and dissolves quickly. Instead of a floss-like material, small spheres of saccharides can be produced to carry the drug. The process of making microspheres has been patented by Fuisz, and is known as Ceform and serves as an alternative method of taste masking. Ceform technology involves preparation of microspheres of the active drug. Drug material alone or in combination with other pharmaceutical substances, and excipients is placed into a rapidly spinning machine. The centrifugal force comes into action, which throws the dry drug blend at high speed through small heated openings. Due to the heat provided by carefully controlled temperature, drug blend liquefies to form a sphere, without affecting the drug stability. The formed microspheres are compressed into tablet.

NanoCrystal Technology (Elan Corporation):

This technology is based on concept that decreasing particle size increases the surface area, which leads to an increase in dissolution rate. Nano Crystal particles are small particles of drug substance, typically less than 1000 nm in diameter, which are produced by wet milling the drug. Nano Crystal colloidal dispersions of drug substance are combined with water-soluble GRAS (Generally Regarded as Safe) ingredients, filled into blisters, and lyophilized. The resultant wafers are remarkably robust, yet dissolve in very small quantities of water in seconds. This approach avoids manufacturing operations (e.g., granulation, blending, and tableting) that generate large quantities of aerosolized powder and present much higher risk of exposure.

Quick-Dis Technology (Lavipharm) ^[62]

Lavipharm Laboratories Inc. has invented an ideal intraoral fast dissolving drug delivery system called as Quick-Dis. This is a thin, flexible, and quick-dissolving film. The film is placed on the top or the floor of the tongue. It is retained at the site of application and rapidly releases the active agent for local and/or systemic absorption. The Quick-Dis drug delivery system can be provided in various packaging configurations, ranging from unit dose pouches to multiple-dose blister packages. Disintegration time is only 5 to 10 seconds for the Quick-Dis film with a thickness of 2 mm. The dissolving time, which is defined as the time at which not less than 80% of the tested film is dissolved in aqueous media, is around 30 seconds for Quick Dis film with a thickness of 2 mm. The typical release profile of an active ingredient exhibited by a Quick-Dis drug delivery system is 50% released within 30 seconds and 95% within 1 minute

EFVDAS (Elan Corporation) ^[63]

EFVDAS or Effervescent Drug Absorption System is a drug delivery technology that has been used in the development of a number of both OTC and prescription medications. This is particularly advantageous for conditions such as colds and flu, for which Elan has modified its EFVDAS technology to develop hot drink sachet products that combine medicines and vitamins for OTC use. The granular contents of the sachets can be added to boiling water to produce pleasant-flavored solutions. In these cases the effervescence of the granulate mixture is modified to accommodate the use of heated water.

Fast Melt (Elan Corporation) ^[64]

It is a highly porous, micro fine matrix tablet. Once placed on the tongue, this matrix rapidly absorbs liquid and disintegrates. The drug, in a stabilized, size-reduced form to ensure optimal solubility, dissolves rapidly. The combination of a mild effervescent base and drug processing ensures that the dosage form goes into solution in approximately 15 to 30 seconds. The drug is released rapidly within the oral cavity, where it dissolves to form a drug solution that is then swallowed. This is particularly advantageous in cases like migraine where a fast onset of clinical effect is required. A portion of the drug solution may be absorbed locally in the oral cavity and therefore may avoid first-pass metabolism in the liver that limits the bioavailability of many drugs. The fast-melt system rapidly disintegrates in the oral cavity; hence, patients do not have to swallow a large cumbersome dosage form, which discourages many from taking their medication. Thus, the fast-melt dosage form combines the benefits of liquid formulations with those of a solid oral dosage form

Multiflash (Prographarm) ^[65]

Multiflash is a multi-unit tablet composed of coated micro granules and fast-disintegrating excipients. This multi particulate tablet quickly disintegrates in the oesophagus after being swallowed with a minimum amount of water. This tablet avoids mucosal adhesion, and coated pellets can match various dissolution rates.

Fast Dissolving Films:**SOLULEAVES™** ^[66]:

Technology is used to produce a range of oral delivery films that can incorporate active ingredients, colors and flavors. SOLULEAVES™ films can be designed to dissolve rapidly on contact with saliva, quickly releasing the active ingredients and flavors. This quality makes edible films an excellent delivery method for a large range of products requiring fast release in the mouth. For pharmaceutical uses this method of administration is especially useful for pediatric or elderly patients who may have difficulty swallowing traditional tablets or capsules. The delivery system can be used for the cough/cold, gastrointestinal and pain therapeutic areas as well as delivering nutritional products. SOLULEAVES™ films can also be designed to adhere to mucous membranes and to release the active ingredient slowly over 15 minutes.

WAFERTAB™

It is a drug delivery system that incorporates pharmaceutical actives into an ingestible filmstrip. The system provides rapid dissolution and release of actives when the strip comes into contact with saliva in the mouth. The WAFERTAB™ filmstrip can be flavored for additionally improved taste masking. The active ingredient is precisely dosed and integrated into the body of a pre-manufactured XGEL™ film, thus preventing exposure to unnecessary heat and moisture and potentially enhancing product stability. The WAFERTAB™ system lends itself to many possibilities for innovative product design, enabling multiple films with different actives to be bonded together.

FOAMBURST™ [67]:

It is a special variant of the SOLULEAVES™ technology where an inert gas is passed into the film during production. This results in a film with a honeycombed structure, which dissolves rapidly giving a novel mouth sensation. FOAMBURST™ has attracted interest from food and confectionary manufacturers as a means of carrying and releasing flavors.

XGEL™ [68]

XGEL™ film provides unique product benefits for healthcare and pharmaceutical products: it is non animal-derived, approved on religious grounds and is suitable for vegetarians; the film is GMO free and continuous production processing provides an economic and competitive manufacturing platform. XGEL™ film can be taste masked, coloured, layered, and capable of being enteric properties whilst also having the ability to incorporate active pharmaceutical ingredients. The XGEL™ film systems can be made to encapsulate any oral dosage form, and can be soluble in either cold or hot water. XGEL™ film is comprised of a range of different water-soluble polymers, specifically optimized for the intended use. All of the XGEL ingredients are well known and generally regarded as safe (GRAS).

Common APIs which are manufacturing as both Fast dissolving tablets and fast dissolving films are listed below in table-5.

Table-5: Common APIs with Brand Names.

API	Category	Fast dissolving tablet brand name	Fast dissolving film brand name
Risperidone	Schizophrenia	Risperdal M-tab	Risperidone energy strips
Ondansetron	Anti emetic	Zofran ODT	Ondansetron ODF
Clonazepam	Sedation	Klonopin wafers	Klonopin wafers
Donepezil	Alzheimers disease	Aricept ODT	Donepezil oral film
Diphenhydramine citrate	Allergy, sinus pressure relief	Benadryl fast melt	Triaminic oral film

Marketed products of Fast Dissolving Tablets and Fast Dissolving Films are listed below in Table-6 & Table-7 respectively.

Table-6: Marketed Products of Fast Dissolving Tablets [69, 70, 71]

S.No	API	Category	Brand name
1.	Ibuprofen	NSAID	Cibalginadue FAST
2.	Piroxicam	NSAID	Feldene melt
3.	Olanzapine	Psychotic disorder	Zyprex
4.	Loperamide HCl	Anti diarrheal	Imodium instant melts
5.	Paracetamol	Analgesic	Febrectol
6.	Olanzapine	Psychotic disorder	OlanexInstab
7.	Montelukast	Asthama	Romilast
8.	Nimesulide	NSAID	Nimulide MD
9.	Mosapirde	Gastroprokinetic Agent	Mosid MT
10.	Domperidone	Anti-emetics	Domray MD
11.	Diphenhydramine and pseudoephedrine	Anti-emetics Anti-Parkinson Agents	Benadryl fast melt
12.	Rofecoxib	NSAID	Zyrof melt tab
13.	Famotidine	Anti ulcer	Pepacid RPD
14.	Rofecoxib	NSAID	Torrox MT
15.	Ondansetron	Anti emetic	Zofran ODT
16.	Mosapirde citrate	Gastroprokinetic Agent	Mosid MT
17.	Rizatriptan	Migrane	Maxalt MLT
18.	Selegiline	Parkinsons disease	Zelapar TM
19.	Loratadine	Antihistamine	Claritin Redi Tabs
20.	Risperidone	Schizophrenia	Risperdall M-tab
21.	Tepoxalin	Canine NSAID	Zubrin
22.	Clonazepam	Sedation	Klonopin wafers
23.	Loperamide HCl	Anti diarrheal	Imodium instant melts
24.	Cisapride monohydrate	Gastrointestinal prokinetic agent	Propulsiv Quicksolv

25 Acetaminophen	Analgesic	Tempra quicklets tempera firs Tabs
26 Mirtazapine	Anti depression	Remeron soltab
27 Zolmitriptan	Anti migraine	Zoming –ZMT and Ramimelt
28 Hyoscyamine sulfate	Anti ulcer	Nulev
29 Baclofen	Anti spastic analgesic	Kemstro
30 Diphenhydramine citrate	Allergy ,sinus pressure relief	Benadryl fast melt
31 Romesetron HCl	Antiemetic	Nasea OD
32 Tramadol HCl	Analgesics	Ralivia Flashdose
33 Zolpidem tartrate	Sleep disorder	Zolpidem ODT
34 Fluoxetine	Anti depression	Fluoxetine ODT
35 Ibuprofen	NSAID	Nurofen flashtab
36 Paracetamol	Analgesics	Calpol fast melts
37 Donepezil	Alzheimers disease	Aricept ODT
38 Alprazolam	Anxiety, panic disorder	Niravam
39 Carbidopa/ levodopa	Parkinsons disease	Parcopa
40 Lansoprazole	Ulcers	Prevacid solu tab
41 Testosterone	Male sexual dysfunction	Straint Buccal
42 Phentermine	Weight control	Suprenzawa
43 Lamotrigine	Anti convulsant	Lamictal ODT

Table-7: Marketed Products of Fast Dissolving Films ^[72]

S.No	API	Category	Brand name
1.	Cool mint	Mouth fresheners	Listerine
2.	Dexamethorphan HBr	Anti allergic	Triaminic
3.	Menthol	Cough suppressants	Suppress
4.	Benzocaine menthol	Cough suppressants	Chloraseptic
5.	Simethicone	Anti flatuating	Gas X
6.	Ondansetron	Anti cancer	Ondansetron ODF
7.	Clonazepam	Treatment of anxiety	Klonopin wafers
8.	Diphenhydramine HCl	Anti allergic	Triaminic oral film
9.	Dextrometharphan HBR	Anti allergic	Theraflu oral film
10	Detrometharphan	Anti tussive agent	Detrometharphan oral film
11	Caffeine	CNS stimulant	Caffeine films
12	Donepezil	Anticholinesterase	Donepezil oral film

CONCLUSION

Fast dissolving tablets having the several advantages compared to fast dissolving films, because large amount of drug can be loaded, no specific packing required. Fast dissolving tablets having the ability to diffuse and partition into the epithelium of the upper GIT. Fast dissolving tablets having the great importance during the emergency cases such as allergic reactions, anxiety, and asthmatic conditions whenever immediate onset of action is desired. If the drug has potential for buccal absorption fast dissolving tablets can confer enhanced bioavailability, by bypassing the GIT and first-pass metabolism. However, if the drug does not have sufficient buccal absorption, and is swallowed, the patient still can benefit from faster liberation, disintegration and dissolution of the drug, leading to quicker onset of action. Moreover, as the dosage dissolves in the oral cavity into a liquid form, it eases the swallowing process.

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